

Oral Presentation #32 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress.

AUTHORS

Hidir Ozer

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1017-2389>

AFFILIATIONS

Unye State Hospital

Department of Neurosurgery

Ordu, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Brucellosis, a zoonotic infection, is common in our country and can also affect the nervous system (Demirdağ et al., 2002; Kandemir, 2015; Özer et al., 1998). Therefore, brucellosis should be included in the differential diagnosis in patients with low back and back pain. Our aim in this study is to share the clinical, radiological and laboratory findings of a patient we diagnosed with epidural abscess and spondylodiscitis and to enlighten our colleagues working in the primary care unit on this issue.

Case Presentation: In 2024, a 60-year-old female patient referred to Ordu University Education and Research Hospital with a preliminary diagnosis of Lumbar Disc Herniation was evaluated for preoperative radiological, clinical and laboratory findings. The patient was admitted to the ward due to loss of strength in the dorsiflexion of the right foot. Lumbar MRI taken after the patient was admitted to the hospital showed spondylodiscitis in the L5-S1 disc space and epidural abscess in this space (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Lumbar MRI images of the patient

Leukocyte: 8000, hemoglobin: 10.9, H CRP: 134, sedimentation: 74, Brucella agglutination test was positive at 1/640 titer, Tuberculin skin test was negative. The patient's history included waist and back pain that worsened at night, fever and sweating. The patient underwent emergency surgery due to motor deficit. The epidural abscess was drained. Culture and pathological specimen were taken. The patient was transferred to the Infectious Diseases Department on the first postoperative day for medical treatment. The loss of strength in the foot improved during follow-up. The patient, whose back and waist pains also decreased, was discharged from the hospital after receiving outpatient treatment. The patient's culture result was positive during follow-up.

Discussion: Brucellosis is a disease that should be kept in mind in the differential diagnosis of patients with back and waist pain due to its endemic nature in our country.

Conclusion: Early diagnosis is very important as it can affect not only the spine but also the central nervous system and cause serious neurological damage. Delay in diagnosis in a patient who could potentially be treated as an outpatient in the outpatient clinic has increased the cost of treatment exponentially due to complications as well as the difficulties it brings to the patient.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Brucellosis, spine, spondylodiscitis

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

Demirdağ, K., Özden, M., Kalkan, A., Çelik, İ., & Kılıç, S. S. (2002). Bruselloz: 146 olgunun retrospektif değerlendirilmesi [Brucellosis: Retrospective evaluation of 146 cases]. *Flora*, 7(2), 120–125.

Kandemir, Ö. (2015). Bruselloz [Brucellosis]. *Türkiye Klinikleri Infectious Diseases - Special Topics*, 8(2), 1–9.

Özer, S., Oltan, N., & Gençer, S. (1998). Bruselloz: 33 olgunun değerlendirilmesi [Brucellosis: Evaluation of 33 cases]. *Klimik Dergisi*, 11(3), 82–84.

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Hidir Ozer

Unye State Hospital

Department of Neurosurgery

Ordu, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1017-2389>

hidirozer@hotmail.com